

MESS: Definitions and Algorithms

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This document provides definitions and algorithmic details of the MESS (Managing Event Stream Summaries) framework. Section 1 introduces the basic preliminary concepts of MESS, including the structure of events, observable units, stream summaries, and their completeness. Section 2 provides the code algorithms that drive the framework, including mechanisms for managing memory, converting events to observable units, and applying policies.

1 Definitions

In this section, the basic preliminary concepts of MESS are presented.

Definition 1 (Event). *Let $e \in E$ be an event that is generated during the execution of a process P . Each event in the log L is uniquely defined as a tuple of attributes $e = (c, a)$, where $c \in C$ is a case identifier from the set of process executions of P stored in L , and $a \in A$ is an activity name from the set of activities of P in L . Please note that we omit the time, as we assume that the events are arriving on the stream already sorted by their emission time.*

Given an event $e = (c, a)$ we use the following notation: $\pi_{\text{case}}(e) = c$, $\pi_{\text{act}}(e) = a$.

Please note that, in our formalization, an event is characterized only by case id and activity name. In principle, however, an event could be characterized by many other properties and attributes, e.g., roles or data values, which, however, have no practical purpose for MESS.

Definition 2 (Event Stream). *An event stream S is an infinite sequence of unique events $S = \langle \dots, e_n, e_{n+1}, \dots \rangle$. It is unbounded, both towards the past and the future. In the rest of the paper, we will use the $\text{observe}(S)$ operator on stream S to iteratively observe one event after the other in a succession.*

Definition 3 (Observable Unit). *As a single result of the $\text{observe}(S)$ operator, we observe one event $e \in E \subseteq S$. We define a mapping function $\Omega : E \rightarrow OU$ to assign each event observed on the stream to an observable unit ou , with $\Omega(e) = ou$, where $e = (c, a)$ and $ou = (c, a)$, and $ou \in OU$.*

Definition 4 (Stream Summary). *A stream summary Sum is an event log, i.e., a subset of the set of possible events $\text{Sum} \subseteq E$. To derive the stream summary Sum we define an event retrieval function $\Sigma : OU \rightarrow E$ that retrieves*

events e and their information, namely their case identifier c and activity name a , from the set of observable units OU .

Definition 5 (Completeness). We defined completeness of a stream summary C_{Sum} with the Jaccard similarity $\frac{|A_t \cap B_t|}{|A_t \cup B_t|}$ between the set of events $e \in Sum$ in the summary that was retrieved at time t (B_t) and the set of all observed events on the stream $e \in E \subseteq S$ until the same time t (A_t).

The expectation is that a summary is capable of capturing the main behavior contained in an observable part of an event stream.

2 Algorithms

This section provides the pseudo-code of the algorithms that drive the framework, including mechanisms for managing memory, converting events to observable units, and applying policies.

2.1 Memory Manager

Algorithm 1 Handling of New Events

Require: Observable UnitHandler OUH , PolicyHandler PH , Stream S

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while true do
   $e \leftarrow \text{observe}(S)$ 
   $ou \leftarrow OUH.\text{converter}(e)$  ▷ example in alg. 3
   $ou' \leftarrow PH.\text{finder}(ou)$  ▷ example in alg. 6
  if  $ou' \neq \emptyset$  then
     $ou \leftarrow OUH.\text{merger}(ou, ou')$  ▷ example in alg. 4
     $PH.\text{remover}(ou')$  ▷ example in alg. 7
  end if
   $PH.\text{updater}(ou)$  ▷ example in alg. 8
end while

```

Algorithm 2 Retrieve summary

Require: ObservableUnitHandler OUH , PolicyHandler PH

```

return  $OUH.\text{inverter}(PH.\text{memory})$ 

```

2.2 Observable Unit Handler OUH for Directly-Follows Relations

Algorithm 3 Convert an Event into a DFR Observable Unit

Require: Event e

```

return  $((e, \perp), \pi_{case}(e), true)$ 

```

Algorithm 4 Merge two DFR Observable Units

Require: $ou_1 = ((a_1^1, a_1^2), c_1, f_1)$, $ou_2 = ((a_2^1, a_2^2), c_2, f_2)$
 return $\{((a_1^1, a_2^1), c_1, false)\} \cup \{ou_2\}$

Algorithm 5 Convert a set of DFRs into a summary

Require: $OU = \{ou_1, \dots, ou_n, c_n, f_n\}$
 $r \leftarrow \{\}$
for all $ou_i = ((a_i^1, a_i^2), c_i, f_i) \in OU$ **do**
 $r \leftarrow r \cup \{a_i^1\} \cup \{a_i^2\}$
end for
 return r

2.3 Policy Handler PH for Sliding Window

$PH.memory \leftarrow \langle \rangle$
 $PH.window_size = 10$

Algorithm 6 Find related Observable Units in Memory

Require: $ou = (p, c, f)$
 $m \leftarrow \{\}$
for all $ou_m = (p_m, c_m, f_m) \in PH.memory$ **do**
 if $f_m \wedge c_m = c$ **then**
 $m \leftarrow m \cup \{ou_m\}$
 end if
end for
 return m

Algorithm 7 Remove Observable Units from Memory

Require: ou
while $ou \in PH.memory$ **do**
 $i \leftarrow$ index of first occurrence of ou in memory
 $PH.memory \leftarrow \langle PH.memory_1 \dots PH.memory_{i-1}, PH.memory_{i+1} \dots PH.memory_{|PH.memory|} \rangle$
end while

Algorithm 8 Update the Policy Store

Require: $OU = \{ou'_1, \dots, ou_n\}$
if $|PH.memory| = PH.window_size \wedge PH.window_size > |OU|$ **then**
 $PH.memory \leftarrow \langle PH.memory_{|OU|+1}, \dots, PH.memory_{|PH.memory|} \rangle$
end if
 $PH.memory \leftarrow PH.memory \cdot \langle ou, \dots, ou_n \rangle$
